

Improved Hybrid Machine Learning User Behavioural Model for Secured Smart Homes

Musa Martha Ozohu
Department of Computer Science
University of Port Harcourt
Port Harcourt, Nigeria
martha.musa@uniport.edu.ng

Prof. Ugwu Chidiebere
Department of Computer Science
University of Port Harcourt
Port Harcourt, Nigeria
chidiebere.ugwu@uniport.edu.ng

Prof. Onyejebu Laeticia Nneka
Department of Computer Science
University of Port Harcourt
Port Harcourt, Nigeria
laeticia.onyejebu@uniport.edu.ng

Abstract— This paper proffers a secured and cost effective model for user behavioural analysis (UBA) in smart homes. The model was built with support vector machine algorithm on a generated dataset on constructed prototype of smart home. The prototype had motion sensors and actuators for data collection and switching on and off of things in the home. Another model called human activity recognition (HAR) was developed with Gaussian naïve bayes to interface with UBA for collection of information from the home. The processor of the system is raspberry pi 4 computer board that runs on Linux-based Raspbian Operating System. The two models earlier mentioned were integrated in the processor. The information generated from the system is processed in the processor and disseminated to things in the home. The Blynk Mobile App was used to interface with the integrated system which enables communication between the system and the end user. Experiments were performed on the constructed prototyped smart home, the results depict a convincing prediction of normal and abnormal situation which contributed immensely to the security of the home. On model evaluation, out of the twenty experiments that were performed, the True Positive value was 11, False positive value was 0, True negative value was 8 and False negative value was 1. This resulted in prediction accuracy of 95%, precision of 100%, Recall of 92% and F1_Score of 96%. This obviously proved that the developed system can provide security to about 95% in smart home which is good and will be acceptable in all standard.

Keywordst; *Internet of Things, Smart home, Human Activity Recognition, Security, User Behaviour Analysis, Anomaly detection.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Security which is core and important aspect of any smart home cannot be overemphasized. Smart home security can be viewed from different perspectives; securing the home from intruders, securing the data generated by the sensors, actuators and other devices from hackers, securing the building and its appliances from disasters such as fire outbreaks by remotely monitoring the home. The advantages a smart home offers often also predisposes it to security threats, hence the need to make security a priority in smart homes.

This paper presents a ML model ‘Sensor-Based Human Activity Recognition’, where a human activity recognition model (HAR) that captures data from its environment and translates them into labelled activities was developed. This paper is aimed at classifying these activities further into patterns which we refer to as user behaviour which can either be classified as normal or abnormal. When the behaviour is classified as normal, it implies the home is in good condition

and there is no threat to it and when the behaviour is abnormal, we say anomaly has occurred and there is a security threat that should be attended to urgently in the smart home.

User behaviour in the context of this paper is defined as a sequence of recognized activities generated from the Human Activity Recognition model which is either normal or abnormal as deduced from the training dataset. The smart home plan in figure 2 was used to generate table 1 using the rules for dataset generation in Table 1.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED WORKS

These literatures on secures smart home model were studied and streamlined as follows:

Serge and Younghwan, (2015), discussed the possibility of recognizing and predicting user activities in two steps: activity pattern clustering and activity type decision. For the first step, classifying so varied and complex user activities, they used the k-pattern clustering algorithm, an efficient unsupervised learning method. Activity type decision was done with Artificial Neural Network based on Allen’s temporal relations. Their experimental results showed that their combined method provided higher recognition accuracy for various activities as compared with data mining classification algorithms. They however suggested the additional use of an efficient feature selection approach called the J48 decision tree to improve the average accuracy and run time performance.

Huichen and Neil, (2016), surveyed existing solutions for enhancing IoT security, they identified key future requirements for trusted smart home systems. They also suggested the gateway architecture as the most appropriate for resource constrained-devices and for high system availability. Support for system auto-configuration and automatic update of system software and firmware were two key technologies they identified for system auto-management. They summarized the existing network techniques that can be used to secure the smart home and also presented two areas of particular concern: system auto-configuration and security updates.

Samaneh *et al.*, (2019), in their work titled ‘Enhancing activity recognition using CPD-based activity segmentation’ recognized that learning human activity model from streaming sensor data is an important problem for the successful realization of intelligent environments. Activity learning encompasses valuable capabilities such as activity recognition, activity detection, activity segmentation and activity forecasting. They tried to enhance activity recognition by

identifying activity transitions. To achieve this goal, by introducing a change point detection-based activity segmentation model which partitions behaviour-driven sensor data into non-overlapping activities in real time.

Mohammed *et al.*, (2018), in their paper titled 'A robust human activity recognition system using smartphone sensors and deep learning' presented a smartphone inertial sensors-based approach for human activity recognition. Their proposed system consists basically of three main parts: sensing, feature extraction and recognition. The sensing part collects sensor data as input, feature extraction starts with the removal of noise to isolate relevant signals after which it does statistical analysis on fixed-size sliding windows over the time-sequential inertial sensor signals to generate robust features. Activity modelling is done by extracting features from the data using deep learning and Deep Belief Network (DBN).

Abubaker *et al.*, (2019), recognized that understanding progressive changes in human behaviour is very important in formulating an effective intelligent environment. The aim of their work "The human behaviour indicator: A measure of behavioural evolution" is to assess the ADLs (Activities of Daily Living) or ADWs (Activities of Daily Working) of a person who lives or works independently in his or her own home or office and present it as a single value for each day which is used to provide a holistic view of the behaviour of the person being monitored and will be used to forecast the behaviour changes of the participant. By inspecting the trends in multiple activities, it is possible to identify and predict human behavioural changes. They referred to trends in people's behaviour as behavioural evolution. Behavioural evolution of a participant in an ambient intelligent environment (AmI) is an indicator of a person's social and health status.

Amira and Ezzeddine, (2017), in their work titled 'Abnormal Behaviour Recognition for Intelligent Video Surveillance System' noted that abnormal behaviour detection is becoming an attractive area of research. They proposed two main steps which is made up of a video surveillance system representing the human behaviour and the behaviour modelling as a measure of behavioural evolution. They described behavioural evolution as changes in the human behaviour over time as indicated by their model.

Jessamyn *et al.*, (2017), in their work titled 'Activity Learning as a Foundation for Security Monitoring' introduced a smart home based approach to home security. They described their approach using the CASAS smart home framework and activity learning algorithms. They detected for possible threats in the home by monitoring for activity-based anomalies. Stages for their activity based anomaly detection included Activity Recognition, Activity discovery and anomaly detection using isolation forest.

Darpan *et al.*, (2019), in their work titled 'A semantic-based approach to sensor data segmentation in real-time Activity Recognition' proposed Semiotic theory inspired ontological model, capturing generic knowledge and inhabitant-specific preferences for conducting ADLs to support the segmentation process. They developed a multithreaded decision algorithm and system prototype and evaluated against 30 use case

scenarios where each event was simulated at 10sec interval. The results suggested that all sensor events were adequately segmented with 100% accuracy for a single ADL scenario and 97.8% accuracy for composite ADL scenario.

Abel (2017), in his paper titled 'An approach to smart home security system using Arduino' designed a smart home prototype for a low-cost and efficient home automation model. Their design focused on wireless flexible and inexpensive smart home system using Mega Arduino board platform. Their system was able to send real-time video and GSM-based messages in cases of fire outbreaks, it was also able to detect motions and also monitor the temperature and humidity of the home.

Aditi and Anjali (2014), discussed in details the role of predictive algorithms in event recognition in smart homes in their paper titled 'Use of Prediction Algorithms in Smart Homes'. They also suggested episode discovery as a means of finding the frequency of occurrences of events so as to target particular events for automation.

Rajeev and Soeng (2013), in their paper titled 'Smart Home-Control and Monitoring System Using Smart Phone' presented a flexible and low cost home control and monitoring system using an embedded micro-web server, with IP connectivity based smart phone app. Their system could perform more than just switching functionalities and did not also require a dedicated server PC with respect to similar systems.

Salman *et al.*, (2016), proposed an algorithm for smart home automation system using sensor nodes which are directly connected to Arduino Nano. The algorithm can switch on and off the lights based on information from the sensors. It can also generate an alarm based on information from the gas sensor. It monitors the power consumption of different home appliances and these appliances can be controlled from any part of the world via the internet.

Rashidi *et al.*, (2008), developed Centre for Advanced Studies in Adaptive Systems (CASAS) at Washington State University. CASAS is an adaptive smart home that uses machine learning techniques to discover user behavioral patterns and automatically mimic these patterns.

The user can modify the automation policies, provide feedback on the proposed automation activities, and introduce new requests. CASAS can automatically identify changes in resident behaviour. The Frequent and Periodic Activity Miner (FPAM) algorithm identifies frequent and periodic activity patterns after Z processing activity information. The patterns are modelled by a Hierarchical Activity Model (HAM) for a satisfactory automation policy utilizing temporal and structural regularities.

III. METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 shows the architecture of the smart home system. The physical layer is made up of Raspberry Pi board, sensors and actuators connected to the Raspberry Pi board which serves as the processor. The sensors used with their respective responsibilities include the motion sensors; for capturing movement, temperature sensor; for identifying changes in the temperature; water sensor; for sensing the flow of water, the door position sensor etc.

The actuators include the buzzer which produces sound alarm when there is a security breach, door control motor that controls the door remotely and the lighting bulbs for turning on and off remotely.

The sensors and actuators were plugged (wired) with General Purpose Input and Output (GPIO) pins of the raspberry pi 4 board. This layer deals with data collection, which goes into processors for processing and signals generated used as inputs in the smart home system.

The next is middleware layer which serves as a support between the physical layer and application layer, such support are communication, networking services. It is made up of the Raspbian Operating System running on the Raspberry Pi board, General Purpose Input and Output (GPIO) library, Blynk Library and Wifi. The Raspberry Pi board of the smart home system is connected to an internet enabled WiFi service via its embedded WiFi module and configured using an external IP address. This was achieved by adding the standard FTP port 21 and 20 to the port forwarding settings of the WiFi. The wifi serves as the gateway network. The GPIO libraries are also imported as part of the middleware layer. The Pi interfaces directly with sensors and actuators through its GPIO pins. The Blynk Library was imported as part of the middleware layer which is an IoT platform for businesses and developers. A script is written which enabled communication with Blynk server which in turn communicates with the home owner's mobile app. The Application layer is made up of the various algorithms and models that make up the smart home. This includes the Human Activity Recognition (HAR) model which was developed with Gaussian Naïve Bayes algorithm and the User Behavior Analyzer (UBA) Model developed with Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm.

The entire system was achieved with of synergy of internet of things technology, machine learning models, mobile software and the Raspberry Pi computer board serving as the processor. This is shown in the high level architecture of the system in figure 2.

Figure 1: Architecture of the System

Figure 2: High level architecture of the system.

A. BUILDING OF MODEL FOR USER BEHAVIOUR

The user behaviour model was gotten from the merger of output from the HAR classifier (activities) and weekday which serves as input features to the UBA model. The user behaviour is defined as different combination of possible outcomes based on valid sequence of activities generated from the Human Activity Recognition model. Table 1 show rules for constructing the training dataset as mapped out from the smart home plan in figure 3.

Figure 3: Smart Home floor plan

Figure 3 is the smart home plan alongside with the positions where the sensors are mounted in the home to capture information which are converted to activities. To create a change in the state of any of the motion sensors, it is triggered by moving a life object (such as a human hand) close to it to sense motion or movement. The triggering of MS01 generates activity called HEN as depicted in table 1. In the same manner, the triggering of MS07 generates the activity Kitchen Entry (KEN). Other activities in the table mentioned above were generated using the same process. These activities were used to generate the rules that were used for dataset generation, such generated data is shown in table 2.

Table 1 has four columns, serial number, activity, activity description, next possible activity and thirteen rows which represents features to the UBA model. The list of the activities on the Next possible activity column are activities that can possibly occur after the one on the activity column has taken place. For instance, in serial no.1, after HEN (Home Entry), KEN, REN, HEX, SNG, DNG, and CAY are the activities that can occur. Outside, the activities for Home entry (HEN) any other activity that occurs will lead to abnormality. For the second row, the activity that took place was KEN (Kitchen Entry) with next possible activities as CNG (Cooking) and KEX which predict normal situation. However, other activities CNG, KEX will result to abnormality. The approach was adopted in generating the remaining rows (activities).

Table 1: Rules for constructing the user behavior

S/N	ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY MEANING	NEXT POSSIBLE ACTIVITY
1.	HEN	Home Entry	KEN, REN, HEX, SNG, DNG, CAY
2.	KEN	Kitchen Entry	CNG, KEX
3.	KEX	Kitchen Exit	SNG, CAY, DNG, REN, HEX, ENG
4.	CNG	Cooking	HEX
5.	HEX	Home Exit	HEN
6.	REN	Rest Room Entry	LNG, BNG, REX
7.	LNG	Stooling	BNG, REX
8.	BNG	Bathing	LNG, REX
9.	REX	Rest Room Exit	SNG, CAY, DNG, HEX
10.	SNG	Sleeping	KEN, REN, CAY, DNG, HEX
11.	CAY	Clothing Activity	DNG, SNG, HEX, REN, KEN
12.	DNG	Studying	HEX, REN, SNG, CAY, HEN
13.	ENG	Eating	KEN, REN, SNG, CAY, HEX

B. GENERATION OF DATASET

Once the HAR predicts an activity, it is automatically saved as the 'Current Activity'. For instance, when HEN is predicted, it means the home owner entered the home. Other activities that can follow home entry are KEN, REN, HEX, SNG, DNG, CAY as seen on the table 1. The current activity is shifted to 'Previous1Activity' once a new activity is predicted. This is as depicted on the sample of the dataset in table 2 and the initial Previous1Activity is shifted to 'Previous2Activity' and the initial Previous2Activity is discarded as it is no longer needed.

For example, in table 2, the first predicted activity was HEN (previousactivity2), followed by KEN (previousactivity1) and KEX (current activity). The sequence of the occurrence of these activities conforms to the rules for the UBA dataset generation and the prediction should result in a YES, meaning that the home is in a normal condition. For the second row on table 2, the first predicted activity is REN (Previous2Activity) followed by LNG (Previous1Activity) and then SNG (CurrentActivity). The outcome of the sequence of these activities should result in a YES, meaning that the home is in a normal condition because it conforms to the rules for the dataset generation. On the sixth row of table 2, Previous2Activity is ENG, previous1Activity is HEN and CurrentActivity is DNG. The sequence of these activities should result in a NO because following the rules HEN cannot occur after ENG.

Table 2: Sample of the User Behaviour training dataset

Weekday	Day Hour	Current Activity	Previous 1 Activity	Previous 2 Activity	Normality
Monday	3	Kex	Ken	Hen	Yes
Sunday	5	Sng	Lng	Ren	Yes
Sunday	7	Hex	Cay	Kex	Yes
Sunday	9	Hen	Hex	Kex	Yes
Sunday	16	Kex	Ken	Eng	Yes
Monday	1	Dng	Hen	Eng	No
Monday	5	Lng	Ren	Kex	Yes
Monday	8	Eng	Ex	Cng	Yes
Monday	11	Hex	Rex	Cay	Yes

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A series of experiments were carried out by triggering the sensors in the prototype smart home. The results that were generated from the experiments are shown in Table 3.

V. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Table 3 show the results obtained from experiments conducted on the prototype smart home, in serial number 1, the first activity carried out was REN (Rest room entry), and the sensor responsible for this activity is MS05, which was triggered. The home owner receives a ‘Movement Update’ alert on his/her mobile device and on the notification details he or she receives a ‘Home in good condition’.

The second activity carried out is LNG (Stooling). This was done by triggering the sensor MS03 which is responsible for the stooling activity. REN becomes Previous activity1 while LNG becomes Current activity. The home owner receives a ‘Movement Update’ alert on his/her mobile device and on the notification details he or she receives a ‘Home in good condition’.

MS08 was triggered next to carry out the third activity, SNG (Sleeping). This sequence of activities: REN, LNG, SNG (i.e Previous activity2, previous activity1, current activity) form a

recognized pattern which is referred to as a behaviour. Based on the training dataset, the expected output is a YES (meaning that the behaviour is normal and the home is safe). The experimental result which is the UBA prediction is also a YES, which means that the prediction is correct. The home owner receives an alert of ‘movement update’ on his or her mobile device and a ‘home in good condition’ in the ‘notification details’. A sample of screen shot of this message is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Interface with the home in good condition.

Figure 4 shows the notification message received by the home owner on his or her mobile device as a result of our experimentation of serial number 1 on table 3. This notification is the same for all instances of the experiment where the user behaviour is normal and there are no security threats. The home owner simply clicks on the OK button as reception.

For serial number 3, MS11 was triggered representing CAY and it became the current activity, KEX which was the initial current activity became previous activity1 and SNG which was the initial previous activity1 became previous activity2 and LNG which was the initial previous activity2 was automatically discarded. The expected output for the series of activities SNG, KEX, CAY forming a behaviour is a NO and the experimental prediction resulted in a NO. The classifier predicted correctly, indicating that an anomaly is detected. An instant message is sent to the home owner alerting him or her of security threats. Figure 5 is the screen shot of the message received by the home owner.

Figure 5: Interface with the home in an unsafe state.

As seen in figure 5, the alert message ‘SECURITY ALERT’ is sent to the home owner’s mobile device. The home owner is expected to respond to the alert by clicking the OK button. ‘Anomaly condition detected’ message is displayed on the notification details. The screen shot as seen in figure 5 is the message received by the home owner whenever an anomaly condition is detected.

In serial number 4 of table 2, MS00 representing HEX (Home Exit) was triggered. HEX is the current activity, CAY becomes previous activity1 and KEX becomes Previous Activity2. The Expected output is YES according to the training dataset but prediction here is NO, meaning that the prediction is wrong. However, security alert as in the one of figure 5 is sent to the home owner.

MS06 (KEX) was triggered in serial number 5, HEX became previous activity1 and CAY became previous activity2, the Expected Output is No and prediction is No, meaning that the prediction is correct. “Security Alert” and “Anomaly Condition” message is sent to the Home owner as in the one of figure 5.

Table 3: Experimental Results.

S/N	PREVIOUS ACTIVITY 2	PREVIOUS ACTIVITY 1	CURRENT ACTIVITY	EXPECTED OUTPUT	PREDICTION	ALERT	NOTIFICATION
1	REN	LNG	SNG	YES	YES	MOVEMENT UPDATE	HOME IN GOOD CONDITION
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS05	MS03	MS08				
2	LNG	SNG	KEX	YES	YES	MOVEMENT UPDATE	HOME IN GOOD CONDITION
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS03	MS08	MS06				
3	SNG	KEX	CAY	NO	NO	SECURITY ALERT	ANOMALY CONDITION DETECTED
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS08	MS06	MS11				
4	KEX	CAY	HEX	YES	NO	SECURITY ALERT	ANOMALY CONDITION DETECTED
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS06	MS11	MS00				
5	CAY	HEX	KEX	NO	NO	SECURITY ALERT	ANOMALY CONDITION DETECTED
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS11	MS00	MS06				

6	HEX	KEX	HEX	NO	NO	SECURITY ALERT	ANOMALY CONDITION DETECTED
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS00	MS06	MS00				
7	KEX	HEX	HEN	YES	YES	MOVEMENT UPDATE	HOME IN GOOD CONDITION
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS06	MS00	MS01				
8	HEX	HEN	KEN	YES	YES	MOVEMENT UPDATE	HOME IN GOOD CONDITION
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS00	MS01	MS07				
9	HEN	KEN	KEX	YES	YES	MOVEMENT UPDATE	HOME IN GOOD CONDITION
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS01	MS07	MS06				
10	KEN	KEX	ENG	YES	YES	MOVEMENT UPDATE	HOME IN GOOD CONDITION
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS07	MS06	MS02				
11	KEX	ENG	HEN	NO	NO	SECURITY ALERT	ANOMALY CONDITION DETECTED
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS06	MS02	MS01				
12	ENG	HEN	DNG	NO	NO	SECURITY ALERT	ANOMALY CONDITION DETECTED
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS02	MS01	MS02				
13	HEN	DNG	KEX	YES	YES	MOVEMENT UPDATE	HOME IN GOOD CONDITION
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS01	MS02	MS06				
14	DNG	KEX	REN	NO	NO	SECURITY ALERT	ANOMALY CONDITION DETECTED
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS02	MS06	MS05				
15	KEX	REN	LNG	YES	YES	MOVEMENT UPDATE	HOME IN GOOD CONDITION
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS06	MS05	MS03				
16	REN	LNG	REX	YES	YES	MOVEMENT UPDATE	

SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS05	MS03	MS04				HOME IN GOOD CONDITION
17	LNG	REX	CAY	YES	YES	MOVEMENT UPDATE	HOME IN GOOD CONDITION
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS03	MS04	MS11				
18	REX	CAY	DNG	YES	YES	MOVEMENT UPDATE	HOME IN GOOD CONDITION
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS04	MS11	MS02				
19	CAY	DNG	BNG	NO	NO	SECURITY ALERT	ANOMALY CONDITION DETECTED
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS11	MS02	WS10				
20	DNG	BNG	REX	NO	NO	SECURITY ALERT	ANOMALY CONDITION DETECTED
SENSORS TRIGGERED	MS02	WS10	MS04				

VI. MODEL EVALUATION

The Confusion matrix of the experimental results on table 3 is shown in table 4.

Table 4: Confusion Matrix of the experimental result.

	Predicted: NO	Predicted: YES
Actual NO:	TN = 8	FP = 0
Actual YES:	FN = 1	TP = 11

As seen on table 4, out of the twenty experiments that were performed, the True Positive (TP) value is 11 (i.e., the number of times it predicted true and it was actually true), False positive (FP) value was 0 (i.e. the number of times it predicted positive when it was actually negative), True negative(TN) value was 8 (i.e. the number of times it predicted negative and it was actually negative) and False negative (FN) value was 1 (i.e. the number of times it predicted negative and it was positive). This resulted in prediction accuracy of 95%, precision of 100%, Recall of 92% and F1_Score of 96%. This obviously proved that the developed system can provide security to about 95% in smart home which is good and will be acceptable in all standard.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this research, a smart-home based approach to home security was implemented in the smart home prototype, where the smart home makes use of activity learning in order to transform the system into one that is activity aware. These activities which are

further categorized formed the basis of the user behaviour which was modelled to secure the home.

This research work proffers a cost effective solution with the design of User behaviour analysis (UBA) model. The research developed a model that is capable of capturing human activities and grouping them into behavioural patterns that stand as a measure to identify normal and abnormal behaviour in Smart Homes.

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